

Second Report on Impact Analysis

D2.9

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Executive Summary

This report constitutes the follow on deliverable D2.8 (M24), that described and monitored the EPOS communication activities during the first 24 months of the EPOS IP project.

On one hand, communication and dissemination of achieved results and progress of the EPOS IP project are key to ensuring the successful development and implementation of the EPOS Research Infrastructure; timely and planned external communications raise the profile of EPOS with the user community and other key stakeholders, which will in turn ensure that EPOS has positive scientific and socio-economic impact. On the other hand, communication allowed a smooth and effective operation of EPOS IP project tasks by facilitating work and networking within the consortium.

Deliverables 2.8 and 2.9 allow for reflection on the communications outputs. These deliverables have mostly concentrated on quantitative review, but as EPOS moves to the operation phase, additional qualitative review involving stakeholder and user feedback will provide the key to understanding the impact that EPOS as a whole generates.

This document, in particular, provides an update on the communication and dissemination activities as well as on the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) attainment at M36 and M48. KPIs were set prior to review and results provide a key understanding of the EPOS communications status and potential impact routes. The deliverable provides a brief overview of the KPIs and progression and includes monitoring data sets.

It is important to stress that statistics presented in this document as at M48, actually take into consideration the period until the end of August 2019 (M47), this to permit the interpretation of numbers and the writing of the document.

Introduction

The EPOS Implementation Phase (IP) project has been a key part of delivering the EPOS long-term plan to facilitate integrated use of data, data products, and services and physical access to facilities in the field of Earth Science. The undertaking incorporates 256 research infrastructures across 139 institutes and organisations, throughout 25 countries and 3 associated partner countries. Whilst undertaking the EPOS IP, the EPOS ERIC, the legal body for pan-European Research Infrastructures was established and subsequently launched in October 2018. The creation and integration of the strategic Thematic Core Services (TCS) and the overarching Integrated Core Services (ICS) e-infrastructure via EPOS as a whole will facilitate the data needs of the EPOS community and key stakeholders.

Communication and dissemination activities are key to generating and maximising the impact of EPOS activities and ensuring sustained engagement and success. Effective communication between the different communities within EPOS including IT experts and scientists specialising in different geoscience fields and the wider EPOS stakeholder and user communities is key to ensuring that EPOS continues to establish and grow.

The communication work package (WP2) is led by INGV, it includes GFZ, UiB, UKRI, IGF PAS, UCPH, ZRC SAZU, TRUST IT and its activities receive input from the entire EPOS consortium.

The period since the previous deliverable has include the launch of EPOS as an ERIC and additional demonstration of the data portal. To ensure that users are aware of these key milestones, target communications to ensure impact and reach have been actioned.

Communication and dissemination throughout the project has been designed in line with the communication plan objectives outlined in deliverable D2.1:

- *engage effectively with stakeholders*, to help achieving this objective, the stakeholders' classification defined during the Preparatory Phase has been slightly revised to disaggregate categories into target audiences (see Table 1); this allows us to focus communication on tightly defined audiences within the broad EPOS stakeholder categories;
- *ensure people understand what EPOS does*, implying to keep the already engaged partners interested and involved as well as attracting further potential partners;
- *change behaviour and perceptions* where necessary, this can be achieved by enhancing the reputation and visibility of EPOS at local, national, and international level and by creating the transfer of knowledge among heterogeneous communities;
- *help achieve the overall EPOS objectives* or, in other words, promote the full exploitation of results, which is the overarching goal of communication.

These objectives formed the basis for the initial M1 – M24 communication strategy, this approach has continued throughout the project where the objectives have been to continue high quality and timely outputs.

1. Methodology

The impact of the EPOS IP communication outputs is important in aiding understand or the stakeholder and user community needs. Impact is the ‘demonstrable contribution research and innovation can make to the scientific field, society and the economy’, communication and dissemination are key to achieving impact.

This analysis of impact undertaken as part of this project has been largely focussed on **quantitative measurements and description of communication outputs**. Measurement of engagement with the communication outputs provides an indicator of reach, sustainability and potential impact.

1.1 Stakeholder Categories and Target Audience

There are a number of key stakeholders each of whom have and will continue to engage with EPOS in different ways. Communication and dissemination have been developed and implemented to be undertaken across different platforms and levels aimed at engaging with different audiences dependent upon the project stage and visibility required. Key stakeholder categories and target audiences can be found in Table 1:

Table 1. Key Stakeholder Categories and Target Audiences for EPOS IP

Stakeholder Category	Target Audience
Scientists	Data Providers
	Data users within the solid earth community
	Data users outside the solid earth community
	IT experts
Governments	National governments
	Funding agencies
	European Commission
Private Sector	Industry Sectors
	Small and Medium Enterprises (SME)
	Large Enterprises
Society	Students at any level
	General public

1.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Strategy and Definition

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) based on engagement with the communication and dissemination actions to quantify and understand effectiveness were determined as part of the Communication Plan (D2.1). The list of EPOS’ KPIs adopted to assess communication impact is displayed in Table 2 (column 1). For each KPI the table indicates the expected outputs by a defined month (24, 36, 48), the achievement at that month and an evaluation of the progress status represented by the ratio between the achieved and expected outputs. Notwithstanding the DoA foresaw to perform the impact analyses at M24 (D2.8) and M48 (D2.9), KPIs were reappraised and assessed also at M36. This additional monitoring step was to ensure activities were continuing to generate the desired impact and, if underperformance was identified, allow time for mitigation. Table 2 reports the preliminary analysis undertaken at M24 (actually M23), the monitoring performed at M36 and the final analysis performed at M48 (actually M47). KPIs at M36 were high or as expected for the majority of outputs excepting LinkedIn posts. This review at M36 provided an overview of status and a chance for reflection on needed actions. Outputs at M48 are as expected or high for all outputs.

Table 2. EPOS IP KPIs Analysis at M24, M36, M48. *High >100%; expected = 100%; Low <100%

KPI Category	KPI	Expected	Achieved	Impact assessment	Impact Analysis*	Expected	Achieved	Impact assessment	Impact Analysis*	Expected	Achieved	Impact assessment	Impact Analysis*
		M6-M23	M23			M24-M36	M36			M37-M48	M48		
Events organised by EPOS	Scientific events	15	66	440%	High	60	70	88%	High	40	48	120%	High
	Governmental events	2	12	600%	High	10	8	78%	High	4	4	100%	Expected
	Private sector events	4	3	75%	Low	5	1	25%	Low	1	1	100%	Expected
Events EPOS participated to	Scientific events	30	115	383%	High	120	230	153%	High	150	168	112%	High
	Governmental events	4	3	75%	Low	7	5	50%	Low	2	2	100%	Expected
	Private sector events	1	1	100%	Expected	3	9	300%	High	0	0	100%	Expected
Participation to projects / initiatives	- Scientific projects/initiatives within SES	2	2	100%	Expected	3	10	330%	High	10	10	100%	Expected
	- IT projects/initiatives	2	2	100%	Expected	3	3	100%	High	3	5	167%	High
	- Other projects/initiatives	2	2	100%	Expected	3	1	100%	High	1	1	100%	Expected
Outreach	Articles	2	26	130%	High	20	26	130%	High	20	21	100%	Expected
	Position Papers	1	1	100%	Expected	0	0	100%	Expected	1	1	100%	Expected
	Press Releases	2	2	100%	Expected	2	0	100%	Expected	2	4	200%	High
	Interviews	10	13	130%	High	10	7	130%	High	1	1	100%	Expected
	Brochure/Flyers/etc.	20	20	100%	Expected	25	20	100%	Expected	12	14	117%	High
	Posters	20	36	180%	High	30	33	180%	High	12	20	167%	High
	Videos	1	2	200%	High	2	6	200%	High	3	6	166%	High
Website	Unique visitors (weekly avg.)	300	440	146%	High	400	421	146%	High	450	512	114%	High
Social Media	Twitter												
	Tweets (weekly avg.)	5	12	240%	High	30	30	240%	High	40	50	125%	High
	Followers	300	620	206%	High	700	854	206%	High	1,000	1,075	108%	High
	LinkedIn												
	Posts/Updates	20	16	80%	Low	6	4	80%	Low	6	6	100%	Expected
	Community	200	2,130	106%	High	2,500	2,549	106%	High	2,550	2,565	101%	Expected
	Facebook												
	Contacts	124	290	233%	High	300	342	233%	High	350	414	118%	High
	Likes	124	291	234%	High	300	335	234%	High	370	378	102%	Expected
	YouTube												
	Channel Subscribers	19	32	168%	High	40	40	168%	High	45	49	109%	Expected
	Visualizations	1,900	3,600	128%	High	4,000	4,000	128%	High	5,000	6,938	139%	High
Flickr													
Views	20,000	21,700	108%	High	27,000	36,000	108%	High	40,000	47,931	108%	High	
Number of pictures	400	420	105%	High	500	502	100%	Expected	650	646	99%	Expected	
Newsletter	Subscribers	800	1,106	138%	High	1,150	1,134	99%	Low	1,200	1,215	104%	High
	Avg. Readers	300	380	126%	High	380	385	126%	High	400	441	110%	High
Training	Training initiatives	15	16	106%	High	20	22	106%	High	10	11	110%	High
	Trainees	300	705	235%	High	900	965	235%	High	230	236	103%	High
	Staff involved in training	12	35	291%	High	30	30	291%	High	30	30	100%	Expected
Intranet	Intranet members	300	640	210%	High	650	680	210%	High	700	1,062	152%	High
	Sessions	—	16,000	—	High	20,000	21,800	109%	High	25,000	28,190	113%	High

2. Impact of EPOS Communication and Dissemination Activities

EPOS IP has created numerous different outputs which have been communicated across different outlets allowing tailored content to be disseminated to varying audiences. Dissemination and outreach materials have been created and a growing social media presence has been cultivated. The key mechanisms with links to view content and statistics are outlined in this section.

2.1 Outreach

EPOS Newsletter

The EPOS newsletter has continued throughout the project with publication approximately quarterly. A full list of issues and article titles and links can be found in Annex 1, Table 12. Content is a mix of information relating to both the TCS and ICS components of EPOS and contributors are from across the EPOS IP project collaborators. The newsletter is distributed via MailChimp with subscribers comprising EPOS intranet users and subscribers from the EPOS website. Subscriptions have increased steadily throughout the project with in average open rate/readers settling around 40%. Some statistics about the Newsletter can be found in Table 3 and Table 4. To date July 2019 there have been 17 issues publishing 102 articles and there are 1215 subscribers.

Table 3. Overview of the Newsletter mailChimp statistics numbers at M48.

		Publication	Date	Number subscribers	% Tot. Opens
EPOS PP		EPOS Newsletter n. 02 February 2014	11 Apr 2014	540	40.30%
Year1	1	Special issue n. 00 / February 2016	25 Feb 2016	889	47.50%
	2	Issue n. 01 July 2016	07 Jul 2016	1002	35.80%
Year2	3	Issue n. 02 October 2016	13 Oct 2016	1029	47.20%
	4	Special Issue December 2016	21 Dec 2016	1058	33.90%
	5	Issue n. 01 January 2017	01 Feb 2017	1076	45.30%
	6	Issue n. 02 April 2017	20 Apr 2017	1076	44.00%
Year3	7	Issue n. 03 July 2017	18 Jul 2017	1113	30.70%
	8	Issue n. 04 October 2017	02 Nov 2017	1115	39.49%
	9	Special Issue December 2017	22 Dec 2017	1134	28.90%
	10	Issue n. 01 January 2018	05 Feb 2018	1130	40.34%
	11	Issue n. 02 April 2018	10 May 2018	1121	40.87%
Year4	12	Issue n. 03 July 2018	30 Jul 2018	1134	41.94%
	14	Issue n. 04 October 2018	31 Oct 2018	1138	29.00%
	15	Special Issue n. 05 Dec 18	20 Dec 2018	1136	32.60%
	16	Issue n. 01 January 2019	31 Jan 2019	1131	41%
		sent again	22 Feb 2019	781	
	17	Issue n. 02 April 2019	30 Apr 2019	1197	46%
		sent again	09 May 2019	688	
17	Issue n. 03 July 2019	30 Jul 2019	1215	42.30%	

Table 4. EPOS IP Newsletter Statistics.

Overview M36 - Total number of Subscribed Contacts: 1134	
Average open rate 39.71%	Average open rate - number of readers 385
Average click rate 12.89%	Average click rate – number of readers 123.75
Overview M24 - Total number of Subscribed Contacts: 1106	
Average open rate 38.48%	Average open rate - number of readers 380
Average click rate 10.68%	Average click rate – number of readers 107.75
Overview M12 - Total number of Subscribed Contacts: 1029	
% Average open rate 43.50%	Average open rate - number of readers 388.6
% Average click rate 15.90%	Average click rate – number of readers 141.6
Overview Preparatory Phase - EPOS newsletter	
Total number of subscribed contacts: 540	
% Average open rate 40.30%	Average open rate - number of readers 213
% Average click rate 16.90%	Average click rate – number of readers 89

Additional to the newsletter, a number of other media outputs have been published including press releases, interviews (YouTube). Branding and outreach materials have been created and distributed at EPOS events including the EPOS presence at EGU which comprised of a booth for information and hub for presentations from EPOS collaborators. A table identifying and quantifying outreach materials can be found in Table 5.

Table 5. EPOS IP Outreach Materials.

Overview of EPOS IP outreach material created and disseminated during official EPOS events				
	Flyers/Brochures	Logo & Corporate	Posters	Gadgets
M12 (2015-2016)	4	2	4	Pins, Stickers, Pens
M24 (2016-2017)	14	12	5	Block Notes, Pens, Bags
M36 (2017- 2018)	16	6	7	Luggage Tag, Bags, Pens
M48 (2018- 2019)	14	2	20	Pins, Stickers, Block Notes, Pens

2.2 Dissemination

The overarching goal of EPOS’s communication is to promote understanding for a full and effective exploitation of EPOS’s achievements. Consequently, dissemination and communication activities served to raise awareness of the EPOS mission and objectives, aiming to increase potential long-term societal and economic impacts. Considering that, these activities have been designed and conducted to ensure effective internal and external communication targeting specific audiences. However, to be sure about the success of the performed activities, criteria for measuring and monitoring the impact of all of the communication activities have been also developed.

A detailed description of the EPOS dissemination and communication activities can be found in the Deliverable 2.4 (M36 and internal deliverable M48). Detailed information and statistics for all sections can be found in Annex 1.

EPOS Website - <https://www.epos-ip.org/>

The EPOS website provides a key dissemination outlet for EPOS materials comprising overarching information on the TCS, ICS and community, the demonstrator portal and links to news, the EPOS twitter feed and key documentation. Between M1 and M23 the EPOS registered over 43,000 (approx. 1869 monthly mean average) sessions and 26,353 visitors. Website visits have continued an upward trend for the second half of the project period comprising 55,922 (approx. 3106 monthly mean average) sessions and 37,544 visitors, M25 - M42. Throughout this period, the information and links to EPOS demonstrator systems have been continually refreshed, with the direct visualisation of the twitter feed facilitating constant changes to the webpage. The most popular EPOS pages excepting the website home page (12,252 page visualisations) were the 'What is EPOS' about page <https://www.epos-ip.org/about/what-epos> (2,817 page visualisations) and data pages including data products (991 page visualisations) and data services (853 page visualisations). The most visited TCS pages included Seismology and Multi-scale Laboratories. The ten most visited pages are outlined in Annex 1, tables 7 and 8.

Social Media

The undeniable power of social media is to allow the creation of a virtual community where there is the capability to share and find information, express opinions, organize events, promote work, meet people. Indeed, social media offer the remarkable opportunity to communicate directly and get in contact with people who share our interests but are far beyond our habitual community. Therefore, "going social" actually works for efficient communications and outreach. As a matter of fact, by using social media EPOS will manage to reach audiences who have less interest in conventional media channels and talk with people whose attention cannot be easily captured writing scientific articles and project deliverables.

The EPOS IP approach for selecting suitable "social channels" has considered the popularity of the platform, the typology of end-users, the level of engagement and continuity required for the specific platform.

Twitter - <https://twitter.com/EPOSeu>

The EPOS twitter feed is an important communication tool for EPOS, reaching a number of target audiences including researchers, policy makers and data users. On July 2019 (M46) we recorded 1052 Followers, 2667 Tweets, 508 Following, 619 Likes (Fig. 1). Twitter provides an instant snapshot of the EPOS community via its follower list and as a platform allows interaction and facilitates discussion in real time. Tweets are also used to publicise, papers, events and other EPOS related news, with sources of EPOS info including EPOS researchers, EPOS newsletter and the wider community. As far as possible tweets and wider topics are planned monthly. The number of followers has steadily grown over the lifetime of the project and has increased from 620 followers in M23 to 1052 M46, where, approximately 74 new followers have signed up per quarter M35 - 42 (see graph Annex 1. Figure 4) and 50-70 per quarter M25 - 34 (see graph Annex. 1 Figure 5 and Figure 6). The @EPOSeu twitter feed is used to communicate in real time, high profile events in the life of EPOS including live tweeting of the EPOS-ERIC launch ceremony in Rome, 7th November 2019 (for further details see Annex 1, Figure 8) and during EPOS events and EPOS attended conferences including EGU and EPOS TCS meetings.

Figure 1. EPOS Twitter Feed July 2019 (M46), @EPOSeu.

LinkedIn

<https://www.linkedin.com/today/author/epos-european-plate-observing-system-63a85412a>

LinkedIn provides a professional networking tool which is often utilised to create communities, share news and updates and provide networking opportunities to individuals both within their organisations and externally. The EPOS LinkedIn account was set up at in October 2016. Therefore, from October 2016 this has been used to building the LinkedIn EPOS community, by first inviting all the EPOS IP project partners and then extending invitations to other relevant researchers. The EPOS LinkedIn community has grown to 2,557 followers.

Topics for the LinkedIn posts were derived from Newsletter articles and from informative material (e.g. from the EPOS brochures, including news related articles and interviews). A post about the legal establishment of the EPOS-ERIC generated interest in terms of additional shares and comments on the topic. The interest surrounding ERIC formation is increasing, as it has been formally established in the fall 2018. Additional information about the EPOS LinkedIn can be found in Annex 1, Table 9 and Figure 15.

Other Social Media Networks – Facebook, YouTube and Flickr.

Some social media channels, not prioritized in the EPOS IP strategy, have continued to grow steadily with increasing content and followers/likes/views (Table 6).

Facebook - <https://www.facebook.com/EPOSeu/>

Facebook has been given a lower priority due to the informality of the network for business purposes. However, the site is used to disseminate events, meetings and ERIC related news which are automatically posted. Within the Facebook community, here are presently (M46, July 2019), 378 community likes and 414 followers with posts often liked and/or shared. Data related to the gender and country split of Facebook followers can be found in Annex 1, Figures 16 and 17.

YouTube - <https://www.youtube.com/user/eposeu?feature=hovercard>

Throughout the EPOS project a number of bespoke videos which include interviews with key EPOS scientists, videos outlining the scope and remit of EPOS. New videos have been added throughout the EPOS IP project and there are currently 22 videos published with 50 subscribers to the YouTube channel. A list and links to the EPOS IP videos can be found in Annex 1, Table 10.

Flickr - <https://www.flickr.com/photos/eposeu/>

The EPOS Flickr pages contain full photographic documentation of EPOS events (e.g albums for the EPOS ERIC Launch Ceremony, EPOS Info Day in Ljubljana and the EPOS presence at EGU). The portal contains in excess of 646 pictures and has received over 48,000 views. Additional information for the Flickr account can be found in Annex 1, Figure 19.

Table 6. Social Media Statistics M24 – M48 Facebook, YouTube and Flickr.

Overview Implementation Phase - EPOS social media numbers - M48		
Facebook	YouTube	Flickr
414 Follower	22 videos – 10 Playlists	646 Pictures
378 Likes	49 subscribers – 6,908 views	47,931 views
Overview Implementation Phase - EPOS social media numbers - M36		
Facebook	YouTube	Flickr
342 Follower	17 videos – 10 Playlists	502 Pictures
335 Likes	40 subscribers – 5,194 views	36,026 views
Overview Implementation Phase - EPOS social media numbers - M24		
Facebook	YouTube	Flickr
290 Follower	17 videos – 10 Playlists	420 Pictures
291 Likes	32 subscribers – 3,600 views	21,700 views

2.3 Training

From the beginning of the EPOS IP project, December 2015 [M3] until June 2019 [M45] the total number of Training events organized by the EPOS community has been 36, attended by more than one thousand representatives of target groups. Target audiences have been the internal and external Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research), data providers, data users, IT experts, industry, NGO. A full summary of the training strategy and activities have been outlined as part of Deliverable 2.6 (M48). These have included a full programme of training courses and workshops which are both specifically linked to the TCS's and also for some of the IT components. The training events were organised both centrally and by specific WP/TCS collaborators. Workshops were often co-located with important events including EPOS specific meetings and also as part of external events e.g. EGU.

The EPOS community has been also very active organizing **meetings (scientific, governmental, with the private sector), workshops and conferences** within the EPOS community and also participating actively to meetings, events, general assemblies organised by diverse organizations. These activities have been outlined in D2.4 (M48).

3. Concluding Remarks

Communication and dissemination activities have been planned and implemented effectively for the full duration of the EPOS IP project. Internal and external communications have been successful in ensuring communication maintains good links within the consortium, facilitates knowledge and work sharing within the consortium and then high impact external communication is the key route for maximising outputs.

The KPIs reviewed in D2.8 at M23 have been updated and reviewed at M36 and M48, this interim review at M36 was a measure to facilitate further planning to deliver targeted, appropriate and high impact communication. At M48 all KPIs are expected or high, continued EPOS activity will ensure more outreach material is created and website visitors are high as the data portal becomes more outward facing. The timely and high impact scheme of communications around the time of the EPOS ERIC launch was a highlight of the communications and dissemination efforts led by the EPOS communications team and the EPOS management office.

As part of the EPOS IP project many of the impact measures have been quantitative. Moving into the operations phase the EPOS communications team would seek to obtain qualitative feedback, for example, EPOS community questionnaires and stakeholder engagement to ensure assess the impact of the information provide and ensure continued information provision. Additional stakeholders and EPOS user groups who access the data and utilise the distributed infrastructure may require differently formatted or targeted information and qualitative assessment would ensure that they are receiving continued service provision and this potentially formal interaction would allow for a feedback mechanism on data provision and service.

Annex 1**Monthly Statistics of EPOS IP
Dissemination and Communication activities****From October 2017 (M25) to August 2019 (M47)¹**

¹ The statistics in this document take into consideration the period until the end of August at M47 and not until the last days of September M48, to permit the interpretation of numbers and the writing of the document.

1. WEBSITE

During the period from **April 1st 2019 to 31st August 2019** the EPOS website registered 15,007 sessions, and 11,199 visitors. During each session an average of almost 2 pages were visited.

Figure 1. EPOS Website Visits April 2019 – August 2019

Table 1. EPOS Website Page Visit Statistics April 2019 – August 2019

	Web Page	Page Visualisations	Percentage
1	/ (homepage)	6,954	19.61%
2	/about/what-epos	1,340	3.78%
3	/tcs/seismology	813	2.29%
4	/data-services/data-products	632	1.78%
5	/events/2019-epos-seismology-workshop-orfeus-annual-meeting-emsc-ga-grenoble-france-7-10-october	537	1.51%
6	/tcs/multi-scale-laboratories/data-services/transnational-access-tna	381	1.07%
7	/calls-tenders	380	1.07%
8	/data-services	356	1.00%
9	/tcs/gnss-data-and-products	334	0.94%
10	/about/who-makes-epos/our-partners	322	0.91%

During the period **from October 1st 2018 to March 2019** the EPOS website registered 22,259 sessions, and 15,671 visitors. During each session an average of almost 3 pages were visited.

Figure 2. EPOS Website Visits October 2018 – March 2019.

The ten most visited pages of the EPOS website are the following:

Table 2. EPOS Website Page Visit Statistics October 2018 – March 2019

	Web Page	Page Visualisations	Percentage
1	/ (homepage)	12,252	21.91%
2	/about/what-epos	2,817	5.04%
3	/tcs/seismology	1,062	1.90%
4	/data-services/data-products	991	1.77%
5	/tcs/gnss-data-and-products	853	1.53%
6	/tcs/multi-scale-laboratories/data-services/transnational-access-tna	696	1.24%
7	/data-services	619	1.11%
8	/about/who-makes-epos/our-partners	583	1.04%
9	/glossary/eric	578	1.03%
10	/tcs/multi-scale-laboratories	566	1.01%

Service-related pages figure highly in the top ten pages visited. In M37-42, the TCS services have been developed in related WPs. In parallel, information regarding them on the various dedicated website sections has also increased. Indeed, 3 (3, 5, 6) of the top 9 pages come from these sections. Similarly, the pages dedicated to data products and data services are the 4th and 7th most visited pages respectively. Keeping up this trend from the previous period of observation is very important in order to be ready for a proficient and fruitful dissemination activity.

During the period from **October 1st 2017 to September 2018** the EPOS website registered 33,663 sessions, and 21,783 visitors. During each session an average of almost 3 pages were visited.

Figure 3. EPOS Website Visits October 2017 – September 2018.

The ten most visited pages of the EPOS website are the following:

Table 3. EPOS Website Page Visit Statistics October 2017 – September 2018.

Rank	Web Page	Page visualisations	Percentage
1	/(homepage)	20,124	21.92%
2	/about/what-epos	3,470	3.78%
3	/tcs/seismology	1,795	1.96%
4	/data-services/data-products	1,636	1.78%
5	/tcs/multi-scale-laboratories/data-services/transnational-access-tna	1,625	1.77%
6	/tcs/gnss-data-and-products	1,300	1.42%
7	/events	1,125	1.23%
8	/data-services	1,017	1.11%
9	/about/who-makes-epos/our-partners	964	1.05%
10	/news-press/news	807	0.88%

Service-related pages figure highly in the top ten pages visited. In M19-36, the TCS services have been developed in related WPs. In parallel, information regarding them on the various dedicated website sections has also increased. Indeed, 3 (3, 5, 6) of the top 9 pages come from these sections. Similarly, the pages dedicated to data products and data services are the 4th and 8th most visited pages respectively. Finally, a third of the top 30 pages come from the TCS services.

This trend is extremely encouraging for the final 3rd of the project when services will be in their final stages and intense dissemination on these through the related TCS sections will intensify.

2. SOCIAL MEDIA

2.1 Twitter

Twitter Account @EPOSeu (31st August 2019). Tweets: 2713. Followers: 1075
Twitter Account @EPOSeu (31st March 2019). Tweets: 2433. Followers: 1003

The EPOS twitter community has continued to grow steadily in this reporting period with the number of followers reaching **1075**. A total of **2713** tweets were done to **August 2019**.

Around **56** new followers have signed up each quarter, as per average. The chart shows that visits to the interest in the EPOS project is consistent and growing.

Figure 4. Number of Twitter Followers between **October 2018** and **August 2019**.

EPOS has also had success in terms of Impressions of the tweets.

Figures below show **the total number of impressions of the quarters**.

Your Tweets earned **131.5K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Figure 5. Number of impression of @EPOSeu tweets between October 2018 and December 2018.

Your Tweets earned **141.9K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Figure 6. Number of impression of @EPOSeu tweets between January 2019 and March 2019.

Your Tweets earned **156.1K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Figure 7. Number of impression of @EPOSeu tweets between April 2019 and June 2019

Chart highlighting the months of July and August 2019

Your Tweets earned **88.2K impressions** over this **62 day period**

Figure 8. Number of impression of @EPOSeu tweets of July 2019 and August 2019

The EPOS community is made up of a variety of stakeholders from the R&I community, policy makers and IT experts. A sample of this community is provided below.

Many prestigious research organisations in the Solid Earth Science field follow the EPOS such Cuenta del Instituto de Geociencias de Madrid (CSIC-UCM) @IGeociencias (9775 Followers), Instituto Geologico Minero @IGME1849 (4574 followers).

In addition, EPOS tweets reach the individual solid earth researchers and scientists, as they are very well represented among the EPOS followers (i.e. Iain Stewart @profiainstewart geologist @EarthSciPlymUni with 26K Followers). Research infrastructures from a considerable part of the EPOS audience on twitter, well known research infrastructures and initiatives follow EPOS on twitter such as Digital Infrastructures for Research (DI4R) @DI4R, European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), Reseach Data Alliance @resdatatall, EOSC pilot @eoscpilot and EOSC-hub @EOSC_eu.

European policy makers are aware of EPOS on twitter, where H2020, DG Research & innovation and e Infrastructures follow the progress of the report.

Research & academia:

Foster Open Science @fosterscience (5330 followers), Instructi-ERIC @instructhub (2771 Followers), Excelsior 2020 @excelsior2020eu (976 followers), The European Research Infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Humanities CLARIN ERIC @CLARINERIC (2401 Followers), Instituto Geografico Aragon @IGEAR_Aragon (1418 followers), The European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC-ERIC) @EMBRC_EU (925 Followers), Geohazards-Tep @esa_gep (622 followers), @womenofgeology (932 followers), @dsarahstamps (654 followers), @figshare (36.3K followers), L'institut de physique du globe de Paris @IPGP_officiel (1706 followers), Instituto Geologico Minero @IGME1849 (4574 followers), @criticalzoneorg (1203 followers), @AuScope (653 followers), @EuroGeoSurveys (1255 followers).

Research Infrastructures:

E-infrastructure reflection group: @eirgeu (577 followers), DI4R Digital Infrastructures for Research @DI4R_eu (499 followers), European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures @ESFRI_eu (1736 followers), Reseach Data Alliance @resdatall (9139 followers), EUDAT @Eudat_eu (3485 followers), EOSC pilot @eoscpilot (1960 followers), @ImperialSpark (9697 followers), @ACTRISRI (735 followers), CERIC ERIC @CERICnews (1344 followers), @digitalities (437 followers).

Policy makers:

Miur - Ministero dell'Istruzione , dell'Università e della Ricerca @MiurSocial (103k Followers), DG Research & innovation @EUScienceInnov (76K followers), eInfrastructures @eInfraEU (3335 followers), Horizon 2020 @EU_H2020 (103K followers), EARTO @EARTOBrussels (5389 followers), @RudolfLegat (1349 followers), the ERIC Forum @ERIC_forum (188 Followers).

Society:

ENVRI community @ENVRlcomm (1127 Followers), Community platform BCquakehelp @BCquakehelp (3555 followers), @soilwaterplant (2313 followers), Scholl Seismology @Schoolseismo (2048 followers), Virtual Multimodal museum @ViMMuseum (1861 followers), citizen science @raspishake (2885 followers).

IT project & experts:

@ResayTec (339 followers), @WiMUSTrobot (536 followers).

Media:

Horizon magazine @HorizonMagEU (7323 followers)

During the period from October 1st 2018 to March 2019 EPOS Twitter reached 273.500 impressions over this year period. The activity on the social media is keeping the number high as per impressions and interactions. In addition, they reached up to more than **eighty impression** in only one day, in the last month which is a high figure when compared to other R&I projects with which the partners are engaged with.

Your Tweets earned **49.7K impressions** over this **30 day period**

Figure 9. Twitter Impressions at the time of the EPOS ERIC Launch - November 2018

Figure 10. EPOS ERIC Tweet Examples - A

A peak of impressions can be seen in figure above “November 2018”. This was due to live tweeting during the EPOS-ERIC Launch Ceremony in Rome on the 7th of November 2018. This demonstrates that the events are a perfect occasion for live-tweeting, involving people in the event and engaging with people not at the event. **Also this was an official ceremony made around a crucial step in the EPOS project’s life. Interaction with followers has also increased when compared to previous timeframes in this reporting period. Some tweets reached interesting percentage of interactions, especially when there is a call to action to be part of the project and the connection with the community is higher.**

Figure 11. EPOS ERIC Twitter Examples - B.

Twitter Account @EPOSeu (1st Sept 2018) Tweets: 2200 Followers: 855

Another peak of impressions can be seen in figure below “EGU2019 April 2019”.

- 9.462 impressions in a day!

This was exactly during the EGU event where EPOS had a booth and participated with relevant speeches from representatives of the project and the EPOS-TCSS

The impact was due to the tweeting during the participation and the constant informative details about the agenda and the top topics of the event.

Figure 12. EPOS ERIC Twitter Example C – EGU peak.

The EPOS twitter community has continued to grow steadily in this reporting period with the number of followers reaching **1075 at the end of August 2019**. A total of 2713 tweets were done to August 2019 on a regular basis averaging at 82 tweets per month.

Figure 13. Number of new followers per quarter 2017 – (June) 2019.

During the period from October 1st 2017 to September 2018 EPOS Twitter reached 354.200 impressions over this year period. The activity on the social media is keeping the number high as per impressions and interactions. Moreover, they reached up to more than 8k visualisations in only one day, in the last month, which is a high figure when compared to other R&I projects with which the partners are engaged.

Your Tweets earned **52.6K impressions** over this **27 day** period

Figure 14. Twitter Impressions - September 2018

A peak of interactions and impressions can be seen in figure above. This was due to live tweeting during the EPOS session at the 36th General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission (ESC) in Valletta, Malta, 2-7 September 2018. This demonstrates that the events are a perfect occasion for live-tweeting, involving people in the event and engaging with people not at the event. The event was significant for EPOS TCS on seismology and a similar peak was also found at that time in visits to the seismology TCS section on the website. Indeed the top 2 Tweets in the reporting period were related to that event. Interestingly, the third top Tweet was about EPOS being included in the ESFRI roadmap, a key policy-related achievement rather than event-related. This demonstrates the interest in news of this type to the EPOS stakeholders.

Figure 15. Top Tweets September 2018.

Interaction with followers has also increased compared in this reporting period. Some tweets reached higher percentage of interactions, up to 7% (see figure above “September 2018”). This is a high figure compared to the average (3-4%) on other EC projects the partners work on.

Figure 16. Twitter Interaction.

The topic about discussion on EPOS status and step 2 of submission of EPOS ERIC has been of interest of the followers, again demonstrating the interest in these types of topics to the audience.

2.2 LinkedIn

Table 4: LinkedIn Posts

Title	Views	Likes
Status on the EPOS Integrated Core Services (ICS) platform: Development to Operation	31 + 1 reshare	8
The benefits of TCS GNSS Data and Products for non-geodesists	29	8
EPOS - The successful 2018 is over: ready to tackle new challenges	20 + 1 reshare	8
The EPOS - ORFEUS Competence Centre in EOSC-hub	16	3
Setting up the legal framework of a complex and multi-organization infrastructure: the EPOS solution	23 + 1 reshare + 1 comment	6
EPOS-NL: the Netherlands contribution to EPOS	18 + 2 comments	12
Top TIPS from IT team: what is the Granularity Database?	15	3
EPOS-ERIC, soon a reality	59 + 8 reshares + 2 comments	30
Validation and Prioritization of the EPOS Service Provision	35 + 1 reshare	16
EPOS-TCS Volcano Observations makes hazard information accessible and searchable	42 + 1 reshare	30
EPOS in GEO	48 + 2 reshares	23
ESM and RRSN - two world class strong motion databases for seismologists and engineers	63 + 1 reshare	7
From Crystals to Mountains: the Multi-scale Laboratories in EPOS	81 + 3 reshares	45
The EPOS contribution to innovation and excellence in science	103 + 5 reshares	25
Wondering what the DDSS Master Table is and what EPOS is up to?	56	2
EPOS: developing the integrated infrastructure for Earth Science across Europe and training the next generation of solid earth scientists	67	11
EPOS: Driving Science	110	18
EPOS: Who benefits?	84	2
Near Fault Observatories in Europe: the road of integration	89	4
The EPOS Legal Entity	38	9
EPOS IP: a collaborative effort for multidisciplinary integration of data & core services from different solid earth sciences & distributed research	81 + 2 reshares	5
Thoughts about the role and ethics of scientific communication, today	74 + 1 reshare	2
Find your way in the EPOS architecture	75 + 1 reshare	2
The EPOS Implementation Phase project Where are we now?	101	-
EPOS a long-term plan for solid Earth science in Europe	88	1
EPOS - The European Plate Observing System	61	1

Some example posts on the LinkedIn account focussing on the EPOS-ERIC.

EPOS-ERIC, soon a reality

Published on August 31, 2018 [Edit article](#) | [View stats](#)

EPOS European Plate Observing System
 European Plate Observing System
[20 articles](#)

 43
 25
 2
 Mes

EPOS - The successful 2018 is over: ready to tackle new challenges

Published on March 27, 2019 [Edit article](#) | [View stats](#)

EPOS European Plate Observing System
 European Plate Observing System
[26 articles](#)

Massimo Cocco

and

Lilli Freda

Figure 17. Example LinkedIn Posts.

3. OTHER SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS

3.1 Facebook

The project’s Facebook page <https://www.facebook.com/EPOS-European-Plate-Observing-System-155473037830465/> was given lower priority, as Facebook is more an informal communication channel, but it has continued to be updated with the automatic posting of news items and newsletters.

Figure 18. Facebook Statistics August 2019 (M47).

Your 5 Most Recent Posts

Reach: Organic / Paid Post Clicks Eng

Published	Post	Type	Targeting	Reach	Engagement	Pro
08/13/2019 6:08 PM	2nd EUROVOLC project Transnational Access TA Call now			124	7 4	
07/30/2019 5:02 PM	Read the EPOS summer newsletter, issue n. 03 July 2019			161	10 12	
07/18/2019 12:14 PM	EPOS ERIC CALL FOR TENDER ► 02/2019 External Auditing			198	8 3	
06/27/2019 4:03 PM	EPOS ERIC at 1st Italian ERIC Forum on ERICs' regulations and			301	31 5	
06/20/2019 3:57 PM	The EPOS Service Coordination Board (SCB) workforce meeting in			168	58 3	

Figure 19. EPOS IP Facebook Statistics (Gender/Country)

3.2 YouTube

The EPOS YouTube channel <https://www.youtube.com/user/eposeu?feature=hovercard>

Table 5. EPOS IP YouTube Channel Content.

	Date of Publication	Video
1	Jul 30, 2019	"EPOS in 3 Words" - by Thematic Core Services Anthropogenic Hazards team
2	Jul 30, 2019	Video interview of the EPOS TCS Anthropogenic Hazards team
3	Apr 29, 2019 12:28 PM	EPOS TCS Satellite Data video, Michele Manunta, researcher at CNR-IREA
4	Jan 29, 2019 4:26 PM	Massimo Cocco, the EPOS coordinator, interviewed on October 2018 at the EPOS IP Annual meeting HD
5	Nov 8, 2018 1:21 PM	EPOS ERIC: a Pan European research infrastructure for solid Earth science HD
6	Feb 5, 2018 2:20 PM	EPOS GNSS Data and Products outreach video as branded content HD

7	Oct 13, 2017 3:43 PM	Sismo-Dance” Workshop-Performance / 18-22 july 2017, Trièves, France HD
8	Jul 6, 2017 11:07 AM	Introducing EPOS: Viable solutions to tackle solid Earth grand challenges HD
9	Jul 3, 2017 11:40 AM	EPOS TCS Geological Information and Modeling (WP15) Francois Robida interview HD
10	Jul 3, 2017 11:33 AM	EPOS TCS Geomagnetic Observations (WP13) Pavel Hejda interview HD
11	Jul 3, 2017 11:11 AM	EPOS TCS GNSS Data and Products (WP10) Rui Fernandes interview HD
12	Jul 3, 2017 10:52 AM	EPOS TCS Volcano Observations, (WP11) Giuseppe Puglisi interview HD
13	Jun 19, 2017 11:07 AM	EPOS TCS Anthropogenic Hazards (WP14), Grzegorz Lizurek interview HD
14	Jun 13, 2017 2:15 PM	EPOS TCS Satellite Data (WP12), Maria Consiglia Rasulo interview, TCS Communication contact person HD
15	May 23, 2017 4:09 PM	EPOS TCS Multi-Scale Laboratories (WP16), Elisa Calignano interview ElisaCalignano rid 20170523 HD
16	May 10, 2017 3:31 PM	EPOS TCS Geo-Energy Test Beds for Low Carbon Energy ((GETB- WP17), HelenTaylor interview HD
17	May 3, 2017 3:38 PM	EPOS TCS Seismology - Florian Haslinger interview HD
18	Apr 19, 2017 11:40 AM	EPOS TCS Anthropogenic Hazards, promo movie HD
19	Nov 3, 2016 12:47 PM	EPOS ICT portal prototype HD
20	Feb 9, 2016 2:38 PM	EPOS Seismology- An Interview with Florian Haslinger
21	Feb 9, 2016 2:24 PM	The -importance of EPOS- an interview with Kuvvet Atakan HD
22	Feb 9, 2016 2:14 PM	EPOS Volcano Observations - an interview with Kristin Vogfjord HD

Hereafter some screenshots from the website of YouTube Google Analytics with some examples of stats: (i) the Numbers of Views of the EPOS videos in the last year, the watch time and the number of subscribers; The average view duration of the videos in the different years; the Top videos, the videos more watched.

Epos ProjectEu

Created: Oct 11, 2011 • Videos: 43

CHANNEL

Oct 1, 2015 – Mar 31, 2019

Epos ProjectEu

Created: Oct 11, 2011 • Videos: 43

CHANNEL

Oct 1, 2018 – Mar 31, 2019

Epos ProjectEu

Created: Oct 11, 2011 · Videos: 43

CHANNEL

Oct 1, 2016 – Sep 30, 2017

Watch time

Minutes

3,781 ▲

Average view duration

Minutes

1:51 ▼

Views

2,037 ▲

Likes

18 ▲

Dislikes

0 ●

Comments

3 ▲

Shares

54 ▲

Videos in playlists

13 ▲

Subscribers

21 ▲

Epos ProjectEu

Created: Oct 11, 2011 · Videos: 43

CHANNEL

Oct 1, 2015 – Sep 30, 2016

Watch time

Minutes

895 ▼

Average view duration

Minutes

1:55 ▼

1 minute 55 seconds
-15.68% compared to previous period
(Sep 30, 2014 – Sep 30, 2015)

Views

467 ▼

Likes

14

Dislikes

0

Comments

0

Shares

4

Videos in playlists

3

Subscribers

6

Top videos ▲

Views · Last 365 days

Figure 20. EPOS YouTube Channel Statistics Pages.

3.3 Flickr

The link to the EPOS Flickr page is <https://www.flickr.com/photos/eposeu/>

In the EPOS Flickr Free account 646 selected pictures have been published until the end of August 2019 organised in several Albums highlighting the EPOS events, infrastructures, instruments, and research activities organised by the EPOS community during the last 4 years of the project IP.

1,000 full-resolution photos and HD videos are the maximum number available for the free account.

Some examples of statistics free available are: the number total views; the number of followers and followings, the number of pictures, the number of tags and geotags, favourite pictures and groups.

EPOS Flickr account has been used only as a repository of pictures with the main goal to share them with all EPOS stakeholders. More activities can be done in the future for example, creating Groups or inviting followers.

Table 6. EPOS Flickr Free account channel numbers until August 2019 (M47)

Pictures	Views	Tags	Geotags	Favorites	Groups	Followers
646	48000	72	7	82	0	5

Figure 21: EPOS Flickr account Album page

4. NEWSLETTER

Table 7. EPOS IP Newsletter Statistics.

N° Newsletter Published	N° Articles	N° Subscribers	Authors of articles	
			Male	Female
17	102	1215	114	86

Table 8

	Publication	Date	Number subscribers	% Tot.Opens	Tot.Opens	% Tot Click rate	Tot Click rate
OS PP	EPOS Newsletter 02 February 2014	Fri, 11 Apr 2014 3:22 pm	540	40,30%	213	16,90%	89
Y1	1 Special issue n. 00 ebruary 2016	Thu, 25 Feb 2016 5:20 pm	889	47,50%	406	17,10%	146
	2 Issue n. 01 July 16	Thu, 07 Jul 2016 11:22 am	1002	35,80%	340	12,10%	115
Y2	3 Issue n. 02 ctober 2016	Thu, 13 Oct 2016 2:30 pm	1029	47,20%	420	18,50%	164

	Sent again	Thu, 03 Nov 2016 1:12 m						
4	Special Issue cember 2016	Wed, 21 Dec 2016 5:58 pm	1058	33,90%	343	1,80%	18	
5	Issue n. 01 January 2017	Wed, 01 Feb 2017 10:51 am	1076	45,30%	426	15,60%	146	
	sent again	Wed, 08 Feb 2017 8:30						
6	Issue n. 02 April 17	Thu, 20 Apr 2017 3:05	1076	44,00%	418	15,40%	160	
	sent again	Wed, 17 May 2017 3:19						
7	Issue n. 03 July 17	Tue, 18 Jul 2017 2:01	1113	30,70%	333	9,90%	107	
Y3	8	Issue n. 04 October 2017	Thu, 02 Nov 2017 5:07	1115	39,49%	425	12,26%	132
		sent again	Thu, 09 Nov 2017 9:59					
	9	Special Issue cember 2017	Fri, 22 Dec 2017 9:38	1134	28,90%	317	6,20%	68
	10	Issue n. 01 January 2018	Mon, 05 Feb 2018 4:26	1130	40,34%	441	12,80%	140
		sent again	Wed, 14 Feb 2018 10:41 am					
	11	Issue n. 02 April 18	Thu, 10 May 2018 2:47	1121	40,87%	450	11,08%	
		sent again	Tue, 15 May 2018 11:07					
		sent again	Tue, 15 May 2018 11:37					
	12	Issue n. 03 July 18	Mon, 30 Jul 2018 2:44	1134	41,94%	469	17,89%	200
		sent again	Thu, 09 Aug 2018 11:29					
Y4	14	Issue n. 04 October 2018	Wed, 31 Oct 2018 5:11	1138	29.0%	324	12,50%	140
	15	The EPOS newsletter Special Issue n. 05 cember 2018	Thu, 20 Dec 2018 11:09	1136	32.6%	365	32.6%	11
	16	Issue n. 01 January 2019	Thu, 31 Jan 2019 3:19 PM	1131	41%	459	20,01%	223
		sent again	Fri, 22 Feb 2019 7:45 AM	781				
	17	Issue n. 02 April 19	Tue, 30 Apr 2019 2:54 PM	1197	46%	544	19,06%	224
		sent again	Thu, 09 May 2019 11:02 AM	688				
	17	Issue n. 03 July 19	Tue, 30 Jul 2019 1:53 PM	1215	42,30%	514	20,65%	251
	sent again	Thu, 05 Sep 2019 11:10 am						

Table 9. EPOS Newsletter Articles and Authors by Issue.

N°	Publication title	Authors	Male	Female	Title of articles
1	First issue n.0, February 2016	PMO, INGV, Italy		2	EPOS announcements and news
2	issue:01 /july 2016	Massimo Cocco, INGV, Italy	1		Dear Reader, Welcome to the EPOS Newsletter! New releases for the implementation phase!
		Massimo Cocco, INGV, Ital	1		From the EPOS Conception to the EPOS Implementation Phase
		Stanislaw Lasocki, Beata Orlecka-Sikora, Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland	1	1	Integrated approach to geophysical hazards induced by exploration and exploitation of georesources - to facilitate the way of attaining excellence
		Vicky Hards, BGS, United Kingdom		1	The Ultimate Earth a future Flagship programme of Horizon 2020 Future and Emerging Technologies
		Vicky Hards, BGS, United Kingdom		1	Earth Science Europe the next steps: Towards an Earth Science Board and a voice in Europe for Earth Science
		Season's Greetings	1		
		Florian Haslinger	1		EPOS at EGU 2016: a booth full of people, a successful session
		PMO, INGV, Italy		1	Meeting of the EPOS Board of Government Representatives (BGR)
3	issue: 02/ October 2016	Keith G. Jeffery, Massimo Cocco, Kuvvet Atakan, Matt Harrison, Daniele Bailo	5		The EPOS vision on EOSC
		Stefano Salvi	1		The GEO Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratory initiative
		Sabrina Bozzoli and PMO		2	EPOS IP project first anniversary: towards the validation phase
		Massimo Cocco	1		The relevance of data integration during the August 24th 2016 earthquake in Central Apennines (Italy)
		Keith G. Jeffery	1		INTEROPERABILITY, PIDs and EPOS
		Lauro Chiaraluce Gaetano Festa Dragos Tataru John Clinton	4		Near Fault Observatories in Europe: the road of integration. Why do we need NFOs?
		Frédérique Mojon Lumier		1	What is EPOS "Geological Data and Modelling" Thematic Core Service (TCS) about?
		Florian Haslinger	1		EPOS Seismology at the General Assembly Meeting of the European Seismological Commission, 5 - 9 September 2016, Trieste, Italy
4	special issue: 03/ December 2016	PMO, INGV, Italy		2	Season's Greetings
5	issue: 01/ January 2017	Keith G. Jeffery	1		Outcomes of the WP06 - 07 IT TEAM meeting
		Elisa Calignano WP16 team		1	From crystals to mountains: the Multi-scale laboratories Thematic Core Service (TCS)
		Alberto Michelini Delia Arnold-Arias Gerhard Wotawa	2	1	ARISTOTLE - All Risk Integrated System Towards The hoListic Early-warning
		PMO, INGV, Italy		2	EPOS @ EGU 2017, session and booth
		Massimo Cocco, Carmela Freda, Daniele Bailo	2	1	The EPOS contribution to innovation and excellence in science

		Keith G. Jeffery	1		What is Metadata in EPOS?
6	issue: 02/ April 2017	PMO, INGV, Italy		2	EPOS @ the European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2017
		Kuvvet Atakan, Daniele Bailo, Keith Jeffery and Matt Harrison	4		Integrated Core Services (ICS) system demonstrator in Prague Integration Workshop
		Agata Sangianantoni, Carmela Freda, Massimo Cocco	1	2	The Board of Governmental Representatives approved the STEP1 submission of the EPOS ERIC establishment
		Keith Jeffery, Daniele Bailo	2		TOP TIPS - Virtual Research Environments, Science Gateways and Virtual Laboratories
		Andrea Tommasi		1	The H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie CREEP Innovative Training Network meets EPOS
		Lucia Luzi, Alberto Michelini, Rodolfo Puglia John Clinton, Carlo Cauzzi Reinoud Sleeman	5	1	ESM and RRSN - two world class strong motion databases for seismologists and engineers
		Keith Jeffery Daniele Bailo Kuvvet Atakan Matthew Harrison			Demonstrating ICS-C Functionalities
7	issue: 03/ July 2017	WP6&7	1		The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) concept and its impact on Research Infrastructures
		Grzegorz Lizurek, Karolina Chodzińska	1	1	Anthropogenic seismicity workshops
		PMO, INGV, Italy		2	The 9th Meeting of the Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on Global Research Infrastructures (GRI)
		PMO, INGV, Italy		2	The 9th Meeting of the Board of Governmental Representatives (BGR)
		PMO, INGV, Italy		2	The 2nd Meeting of the Board of National Scientific Representatives (BNSR)
		Alberto Michelini	1		The Milano and Rome EPOS harmonization meetings
		Lilian Féres		1	GLASS is a unique open access platform for Earth science research
		Marti Michèle		1	SERA and EPOS: a perfect match
		Claire André	1		blueSeis, a revolution in the history of geosciences!
		Roberto Basili	1		Probabilistic TSUnami hazard MAPS for the NEAM Region: the TSUMAPS-NEAM Project
8	issue: 04/ October 2017				Progress in EPOS Authentication and Authorisation Solutions
		Massimo Cocco, Lilli Freda, Kuvvet Atakan, Joern Lauterjung, Kauzar Saleh Contell	3	2	Validation and Prioritization of the EPOS Service Provision
		PMO, INGV, Italy		2	EPOS @ the EGU 2018 General Assembly in Vienna, 8 - 13 April 2018
		PMO, INGV, Italy		2	EPOS INFO-DAY in the Eastern Adriatic Area
		Jean Robert Grasso	1		"Sismo-Dance" Workshop-Performance
		Florian Haslinger	1		The PSHA workshop outcomes
		Michela Vellico		1	Cooperation with ECCSEL
		Sara Barsotti		1	EPOS-TCS Volcano Observations makes hazard information accessible and searchable

9	special issue: 05/ December 2017	PMO, INGV, Italy		2	Season's Greetings
10	issue: 01/ January 2018	PMO, INGV, Italy		2	EPOS is on its way to Step 2 submission of the EPOS-ERIC
		PMO, INGV, Italy		2	EPOS session and booth @ the EGU 2018 in Vienna, 8-13 April 2018
		Kuvvet Atakan, Daniele Bailo, Matthew Harrison, Keith Jeffery, Jan Michalek, Karen Tellefsen	5	1	Status update from the EPOS WP6 and 7 IT Team
		Federica Magnoni, Emanuele Casarotti Iraklis Klampanos	2	1	DARE to tame the Extremes
		Silvia Peppoloni, Giuseppe Di Capua	1	1	The Cape Town Statement on Geoethics and the IAPG network
		Elisa Calignano Emilio L. Pueyo Morer Matthias Rosenau Fred Beekman	3	1	First impressions EPOS Multi-scale laboratories Trans-national access pilot program
11	issue: 02/ April 2018	Massimo Cocco, Carmela Freda	1	1	EPOS-ERIC, soon a reality
		Daniele Bailo, Karen Tellefsen	1	1	EPOS Data policy and the FAIR principles
		Laura Baracchi, Florian Haslinger	1	1	Winding up after an exciting EGU2018 week in Vienna
		Stanka Šebela, Giovanna Maracchia, Lilli Freda, Massimo Cocco, Grzegorz Lizurek	2	3	EPOS Info-Day, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 29 - 30 May, 2018
		Aude Chambodut Simon Flower Pavel Hejda , Maxim Smirnov Alan Thomson Ari Viljanen	5	1	The Geomagnetic field between Earth's core and space: how the Geomagnetic Observations "EPOS Thematic Core Services" (TCS) address the various sources of the Geomagnetic field
		Dorota Olszewska, Grzegorz Lizurek and EPOS PL team	1	1	EPOS PL polish national contribution towards EPOS infrastructure
12	issue: 03/ July 2018	Chris Card, Christian Rønnevik, Xiaoliang Wang	3		New developments of the EPOS-ICS-C GUI, Graphical User Interface
		Lilian Féres		1	EPOS TCS GNSS Data and Products represented at the 36th General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission in Malta, 2 - 7 September 2018
		Frédérique Mojon		1	EPOS involved in the process of open standards implementation for the scientific community
		Karolina Chodzińska Branicka		1	EPOS Thematic Core Services Anthropogenic Hazards (TCS AH) (WP14) Workshop and Annual Meeting outcomes
		Stanka Šebela		1	EPOS INFO-DAY outcomes, 29 - 30 May 2018, Ljubljana, Slovenia
		Florian Haslinger	1		EPOS Seismology activities at the ESC 2018 in Malta, 2 - 7 September 2018
		Machiel Bos	1		Quality Controlled TCS GNSS Data and Products
		Luca Trani and the EPOS-ORFEUS-CC Team	1		The EPOS - ORFEUS Competence Centre in EOSC-hub
		Elisa Calignano Reinoud Sleeman Anke Dählmann Martyn Drury	2	2	EPOS-NL: the Netherlands contribution to EPOS
		Joao Fonseca Andreas Reitbrock Aude Chambodut	2	1	Validation of EPOS services

13	Issue n. 04 October 2019	Pierre-Louis Bazin, Helle A. Pedersen and the EPOS WP04 team	1	1	Setting up the legal framework of a complex and multi-organization infrastructure: the EPOS solution
		Grzegorz Lizurek	1		Anthropogenic seismicity induced by the filling of water reservoirs in Vietnam
		Yvonne Schavemaker		1	GeoERA starts with 15 projects to deliver a European Geological Knowledge Base
		Thanassis Ganas	1		Reliable strain rate computation with EPOS GNSS data
		PMO, INGV, Italy		2	EPOS @EGU2019 in Vienna, 07-12 April 2019
		Glenda Jones			EPOS at the 2018 Science is Wonderful! Europeans Researchers' Night!
		Jan Xiaoliang Kuvvet Atakan Michalek Wang	3		What is a Granularity Database?
14	The EPOS newsletter Special Issue n. 05 December 2018	PMO, INGV, Italy		2	Wishing you every happiness and a prosperous and successful New Year
15	Issue n. 01 January 2019	Massimo Cocco and Lilli Freda	1	1	EPOS - The successful 2018 is over: ready to tackle new challenges
		Anne Socquet, Rui Fernandes, Machiel Bos, Paul Crocker and Lílian Féres	3	2	The benefits of TCS "GNSS Data and Products" for non-geodesists
		Kristín Vogfjorð		1	EUROVOLC – A European Network of Observatories and Research Infrastructures for Volcanology
		Florian Haslinger, Laurentiu Danciu	2		EFEHR Governance: the path to research cooperation and alliance success
		Glenda Jones		1	IS-EPOS Platform Training Workshop at Keele University, U.K.
		Richard Wessels	1		Outcomes of TCS WP16 (Multi-scale laboratories) Annual meeting at Barcelona, November 2018
16	Issue n. 02 April 2019	Keith Jeffery, Jan Michalek	2		ICS-TCS Workshops
		Adrian Stanica, Michael Schultz, Maria Ionescu and the DANUBIUS-PP Consortium	2	1	DANUBIUS-RI, Making River-Sea Systems Work

		Janine Sarah Aeberhard, Michèle Marti, ETHZ Switzerland		2	SERA Progress and EPOS Integration
		Grzegorz Lizurek	1		Anthropogenic seismicity – IS-EPOS platform workshop for students at Geosfera 2019
		Johannes Schweitzer	1		H2020 TURNkey Project Awarded
		Chris Card, Keith Jeffery	2		Status on the EPOS Integrated Core Services (ICS) platform: Development to Operation
17	ssue n. 03 July 2019	Andreas Petzold, Ari Asmi, Daniela Franz and Magdalena Brus	2	2	Providing environmental FAIR data and services for society, innovation and research
		Susanna Falsaperla, Danilo Reitano	1	1	The 3DTelC European project: a new approach to Teaching, Learning and Communicating the science of geohazards in terrestrial and marine environments
		Arnau Folch	1		Riding the wave of the future in supercomputing: Center of Excellence for Exascale in Solid Earth (ChEES) will share Exascale-compatible codes on EPOS repository
		Stefan Wiemer and Banu Mena Cabrera	1	1	RISE: REAL-TIME EARTHQUAKE RISK REDUCTION FOR A RESILIENT EUROPE
		Felix Halpaap, Jan Michalek	2		EPOS Workshops with the User Feedback Group
		Aude Chambodut, Juan José Curto, Simon Flower, Pavel Hejda, Maxim Smirnov, Alan Thomson, Ari Viljanen	6	1	EPOS TCS Geomagnetic Observations (WP13) Meeting with data users and providers, Prague, June 2019
		Richard Wessels	1		TCS Multi-scale laboratories (WP16) final EPOS-IP meeting in Montpellier, June 2019
		Glenda Jones		1	EPOS TCS-Anthropogenic Hazards - May 2019 Events in Pisa, Italy
		Karen Tellefsen		1	EPOS-Norway had its second portal testing workshop
		Luca Trani, Rossana Paciello,	1	1	Representing cross-disciplinary knowledge in solid-Earth sciences with EPOS-DCAT-AP

. EVENTS ORGANIZED BY EPOS & EXTERNAL EVENTS
Table 10. EPOS IP Events * Note: each month WP6 and WP7 organise teleconferences.

Overview - EPOS Implementation Phase events - M48												
Total number of events: 806												
WP name	Events organised by EPOS - M12	Events EPOS participated to - M12	Tot	Events organised by EPOS - M24	Events EPOS participated to - M24	Tot	Events organised by EPOS - M36	Events EPOS participated to - M36	Tot	Events organised by EPOS - M48	Events EPOS participated to - M48	Tot
WP1-2	24	32	56	26	23	49	17	12	29	26	38	64
WP3	2	2	4	2	0	2	/	3	3	1	4	5
WP4	/	/	0	/	1	1	/	3	3	1	2	3
WP5	2	1	3	/	1	1	/	3	3	-	1	1
WP6/7 *	2	3	5	7	11	18	1	4	5	9	9	18
WP8	12	7	19	9	9	18	4	7	11	3	15	18
WP9	3	17	20	1	7	8	3	4	7	-	10	10
WP10	2	8	10	1	7	8	2	13	15	1	21	22
WP11	1	6	7	3	7	10	2	6	8	2	7	9
WP12	5	15	20	3	9	12	4	7	11	3	9	12
WP13	4	9	13	3	6	9	1	7	8	1	5	6
WP14	5	23	28	3	8	11	6	12	18	14	16	30
WP15	5	15	20	4	21	25	1	11	12	-	5	5
WP16	6	13	19	3	20	23	4	13	17	5	9	14
WP17	2	3	5	1	4	5	2	6	8	1	1	2
			229				200				158	219

6. INTRANET

During the period from January 1st 2019 to August 31st 2019, the EPOS Intranet website registered 2.819 sessions, and 1062 visitors. During each session an average of more than 3 pages were visited. In this period of time we can highlight a Bounce Rate of 46.29%

During the period from October 1st 2018 to December 31st 2018 the EPOS Intranet website registered 1.170 sessions, and 427 visitors. During each session an average of more than 3 pages were visited.

During the period **from September 2017 to September 2018** the EPOS Intranet website registered 5.206 sessions, and 1.222 visitors. During each session an average of 4 pages were visited. During the period **from October 1st 2016 to September 30th 2017** the EPOS Intranet website registered 8.402 sessions, and 1.643 visitors. During each session an average of more than 4 pages were visited.

In the second period of time (from Oct 2016 to September 2017) we can highlight a high element of retention of the users and the sessions per user have increased in number.

During the period **from January 1st 2016 to September 30th 2016** the EPOS Intranet website registered 8.290 sessions, and 1.681 visitors. During each session an average of more than 6 pages were visited.

Group activities within the Intranet are shown in the tables **below to March 2019**

Table 11. EPOS Intranet Group Activities.

Group	Members	Posts
AAAI	46	13
AB	12	96
APIs	51	73
Architecture Group	47	10
BGR	35	242
BNSR	30	261
Documentation group	46	22
EC	6	7
EEP	11	8
Epos groups	44	4
EthicsWG	11	96
Global	780	539
GUI	50	87
HG01 Seismological Data	8	4
HG02 Geodetic data	10	4

HG03 Satellite data	7	4
HG04 Magnetic data	7	3
HG05 Geology	9	4
HG06 Episodes	19	4
HG07 Geohazards	16	4
HG08 Georesources	16	4
HG09 Geochemical data	13	10
HG10 3D/4D structural models	10	4
HG11 Analog and numerical models	10	3
HG12 Borehole data	13	4
HG13 Rock sample properties	8	4
HG14 EQ parameters	10	5
HG15 Meteo parameters	6	5
HG17 Georesource production data	10	4
HG19 Transnational Access (TNA)	17	30
HG20 Active seismic data	5	4
ICS technical bulletin	7	8
INGV	64	16
IPC	58	169
JRU Italia	18	91
Messaging System	47	4
Metadata Group	51	169
Newsletter Editorial Board	17	58
PDB	19	791
PID/UID	46	5
PMO	16	143
Private space test	0	0
Requirements and Use Cases group	47	72
SCB	35	571
Support	8	1066
Support2	2	2
System Orchestrator	46	12
TCS - Communication	54	80
TCS - Financial	40	50
TCS - Harmonization	51	33
TCS - IT	62	60
TCS - Legal & Governance	39	29
TCS MSL Consortium Board	11	42
Test Group	9	31
Test-INGV	6	29

TESTING_PMO	6	1260
UFG	44	11
Women in EPOS	4	22
Work Force SCB	11	64
Workflow	48	6
Working Group Implementing Rules	9	28
WP Leaders	41	259
WP01	13	187
WP02	25	98
WP03	17	68
WP04	12	141
WP05	13	76
WP06 & WP07	71	708
WP08	81	96
WP09	56	282
WP10	55	1085
WP11	90	215
WP12	27	127
WP13	20	551
WP14	55	273
WP15	47	674
WP15 Active seismic	8	5
WP15 Boreholes	21	12
WP15 Geology	4	4
WP15 Georesources	3	4
WP15 Models	7	5
WP15 Rock Sample Properties	5	4
WP16	121	448
WP16 Analogue Modelling	19	80
WP16 Analytical	20	28
WP16 Paleomag	14	32
WP16 Rock physics	16	10
WP16 Task Leaders	16	598
WP17	15	66